

IX SEMINÁRIO INTERNACIONAL DE HABILIDADES SOCIAIS

&
I CONGRESSO INTERNACIONAL DE RELAÇÕES
INTERPESSOAIS E HABILIDADES SOCIAIS

25 A 27 DE
SETEMBRO DE 2024

Transforming Social Skills Training: The Role of the Metaverse in the Health Sector

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Abstract

This paper explores how the metaverse is revolutionizing soft skills training in the healthcare sector. The advantages of immersive technologies to improve critical competencies such as effective communication, empathy and collaboration are analyzed. In addition, the challenges and ethical considerations associated with their implementation are addressed, providing a comprehensive view of their impact on clinical and educational practice.

Introduction

The metaverse, understood as a shared virtual universe integrating technologies such as virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR) and advanced computer graphics, has evolved significantly since its initial conceptualization in the 1990s. Today, it is presented as a platform with the potential to transform human interaction, learning and work. In healthcare, it offers simulated environments that allow professionals and students to develop and hone essential social skills in a controlled and safe context. (García Jiménez et al., 2023; León Rubio et al., 2022).

Soft skills, which include effective communication, empathy and teamwork, are fundamental to quality clinical practice. These competencies directly influence the relationship between professionals and patients, user satisfaction and health outcomes (Cantero-Sanchez et al., 2021; Vázquez Morejón et al., 2023). However, traditional training of these skills often faces limitations, such as the lack of realistic scenarios or supervised practice opportunities. In this context, virtual reality and metaverse emerge as an innovative solution to overcome these barriers (Dellazizzo et al., 2020; Oliveira et al., 2021).

Objective

This study aims to analyze the impact of the metaverse on soft skills training in the healthcare sector. It seeks to explore how these technologies can improve interaction between professionals and patients, foster collaborative practices among multidisciplinary teams, and evaluate their effectiveness compared to traditional teaching methods.

Method

The integration of the metaverse into soft skills training was structured in four pedagogical stages:

1. **Initial instruction and training:** participants received detailed guidance on the skills to be developed, such as communication strategies to simplify complex medical concepts during consultations.

2. **Modeling of behaviors:** Demonstrations of appropriate behaviors were presented through videos or guided simulations, allowing participants to observe exemplary practices.
3. **Practice behaviors:** Participants applied skills in specific virtual environments, such as offices, emergency rooms or multidisciplinary team meetings, designed to provide realistic challenges.
4. **Feedback and generalization:** At the end of each session, detailed performance feedback was provided, reinforcing skills for transfer to real situations.

The metaverse used included customizable avatars and interactive environments that replicate everyday situations in the clinical setting, offering an immersive experience.

Figure 1. Representation of different scenarios of the Carmides Metaverse.

Results

Preliminary results highlight the positive impact of the use of the metaverse in social skills training:

- **Acceleration of the learning curve:** participants showed faster learning of soft skills compared to traditional methods, thanks to repeated practice in controlled scenarios and real-time feedback.
- **Increased confidence:** Practitioners reported greater confidence when facing challenging situations, such as communicating difficult diagnoses or resolving conflict in teams.
- **More consistent results:** The ability to simulate diverse interactions reduced variability in participant performance, ensuring greater uniformity in clinical practices.

In addition, the metaverse provided a safe environment for learning, where errors can be corrected without negative consequences for real patients.

Challenges and Ethical Considerations

Despite the benefits, implementing the metaverse in the healthcare sector presents significant challenges:

1. **Costs and resources:** initial investment in technology, infrastructure and staff training can be high, limiting its accessibility in some institutions.
2. **Technological adaptation:** Healthcare professionals, especially those less familiar with technology, may face difficulties in the transition to the use of virtual environments.
3. **Ethical and privacy issues:** The collection and storage of user data in the metaverse raises concerns about the protection and confidentiality of information.

It is essential to ensure that avatar-mediated interaction does not completely replace direct human interaction, preserving the empathic and humanized nature of healthcare practices.

Discussion

The use of the metaverse in social skills training represents a significant innovation, but its implementation requires careful planning. Simulated environments allow for personalization of learning, facilitating practitioners to practice specific skills in varied contexts. However, there is a need to balance the use of technology with the development of competencies in real contexts.

Future studies should focus on long-term evaluation of the impact of the metaverse, including transfer of skills to real situations and patient and team perceptions.

Conclusions and Future Perspectives

The metaverse is a promising tool for soft skills training in the healthcare sector. Its ability to create realistic scenarios and provide immediate feedback makes it particularly effective for critical skills development. However, technological and ethical challenges must be carefully managed to ensure its sustainable adoption.

The future of the metaverse in the healthcare sector is encouraging, with potential applications in areas such as telemedicine, medical education and rehabilitation. As the technology advances, its impact on clinical practice and professional training is expected to become even more significant.

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